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An inorganic–organic hybrid material based on a Keggin-type polyoxometalate@Dysprosium as an effective and green catalyst in the synthesis of 2-amino-4H-chromenes via multicomponent reactions

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Abstract

A novel inorganic–organic hybrid, $[\text{Dy}_4(\text{PDA})_4(\text{H}_2\text{O})_{11}(\text{SiMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40})] \cdot 7\text{H}_2\text{O}$ denoted as (POM@Dy-PDA), based on a lanthanide cluster, a Keggin-type polyoxomolybdate, and PDA (1,10-phenanthroline-2,9-dicarboxylic acid) was prepared and fully characterized by elemental analysis, Fourier-transform infrared and UV–Vis spectroscopies, thermogravimetric analysis, powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD), and single-crystal X-ray diffraction. The structural analysis study showed that the $[\text{SiMo}_{12}\text{O}_{40}]^{4-}$ ions reside in the interspace between two cationic layers as discrete counterions and are not coordinated to the rare-earth ions. Significantly, this hybrid catalyst is a rare case of an inorganic–organic hybrid polyoxometalate (POM) with a PDA ligand based on CSD search (CSD version 5.40/November2018). The hybrid catalyst was further characterized via powder X-ray diffraction (PXRD) pattern at room temperature

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which indicated the good phase purity of the catalyst. BET and Langmuir surface area analysis indicate surface area of POM@Dy-PDA 6.6 and 51.3 m²g⁻¹, respectively. The catalytic activity of the hybrid catalyst was successfully examined in the synthesis of 2-amino-4H-chromene derivatives through a multicomponent reaction. A three-component, one-pot reaction involving differently substituted benzaldehydes, resorcinol/ α -naphthol/ β -naphthol/4-hydroxycoumarin/3-methyl-4H-pyrazole-5(4H)-one, and malononitrile or ethyl cyanoacetate in the presence of a catalytic quantity of the aforementioned hybrid catalyst in EtOH/H₂O under reflux condition gave the corresponding highly functionalized 2-amino-4H-chromenes in satisfactory yields. The catalyst can be reused several times without appreciable loss in its catalytic activity.

Keywords: 2-amino-4H-chromenes, Heteropoly acids, inorganic–organic hybrid, Keggin, polyoxometalates